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Abstract: *The study focused on “Influence of Home Environment on Pupils’ Achievement in English Language”. The research adopted the correlational design method. The study population comprised public primary schools in Kuje Area Council. The target population was 4336 primary five pupils in 880 public primary schools. Multistage sampling technique was used to select Kuje Area Council out of the six area councils, while simple random sampling was used to select four public primary schools out of the 105 schools from which the sample size of 360 pupils were chosen. A stratified sampling method was used to select primary five pupils across gender. The instruments tagged “Home Environment Support Questionnaire” (HESQ) consisting of nine (9) items and “Pupils’ Interaction and Achievement Questionnaire” (PIAQ) consisting of seven (7) items were developed by the researcher and administered on the pupils. The reliability of the instrument was established by administering the instrument on ten pupils that were not involved in the study through a test-retest method. A correlation coefficient of 0.64 was established. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlations Co-efficient (PPMC). Two major findings were established that: home environment influences pupils’ academic achievement in English Language in school, and interaction among family members in English language has tremendous impact on the academic achievement of pupils. The research recommended that: parents should deliberately participate in their children’s learning of English language as a subject in school.*

Key words: Environment, Home environment, Home-support, Academic performance, Performance variables

Introduction

Environment is a significant factor in the life of every individual, especially that of a child. According to the Ecological Theory of Learning by Urie Bronfenbrenner (1917- 2005) cited in a study by Jones and Roundy (2023) a person's development is influenced by everything in the surrounding environment and social interactions within it. Similarly, Miller and Reilly (2018) pointed out that the child is largely influenced by the environment in which he or she grows, and it further asserted that environment impacts on the child's ability to interact with new knowledge and experience. Miller and Reilly opined that environment fosters healthy cognitive and emotional development by offering supportive resources needed by the child to get prepared for the rigours of learning and to adjust to the demands of the society.

In the context of education, environment is a learning ground where the child is exposed to the nuances of acquiring knowledge and the understanding of the society within which he or she grows. Nwachukwu, Onwukwe, Evans-Kemka, Azorji, and Ngumah, (2024) classified environment into two: the physical and psychological environments. According to Nwachukwu et al, the physical environment deals with the material aspects such as infrastructure, availability of resource facilities, while the psychological environment includes the home, school, community, and significant other people such as parents, siblings and peers. The classification agrees with Anene (2003) that environment could be physical, social and abstract', and may also include people, parents, sibling and peers.

Lewin (2018) cited in Nwachukwu et al (2024), used the term 'life-space' to describe the psychological environment. In a further description of the psychological environment, Lewin asserted that the psychological environment is a tool that aides the understanding of the personality of an individual, and Nwizu (2013) equally posited that environment in which the learner acquires knowledge can have tremendous impact on the cognitive achievement of the learner.

Previous studies had shown that both the physical environment and the psychological environment are crucial variables to consider when looking at the likely effects on pupils' academic performance (Olatunji, Aghimien, Oke, and Olushola, (2016), (Al- Shamari, Saguban, Pasay-an, Altheban, and Al-Shamari, (2017), (Onwukwe, Anyanwu and Agommuoh, 2017) and Onyekwere et al (2018). They noted that institutional, psychological, pedagogical, social and demographic variables have significant contributions to the performance of learners.

An aspect of the psychological environment- the home- has been considered as a key influencer of a child's academic performance. The analysis of cognitive theory by Malik (2002) described the home as the first and most insistent of subtle influence on the educational development of the child, because the child has the tendency to interact with the environment, and it further noted that 'the home' is where the learner gets maximum concentration.

Similarly, Umudi, (2025) asserted that the home is the first environment where the child is exposed to both the informal and formal education and training, and is equally where the culture and values of the society are acquired. The researcher also indicated that the child's family provides the foundation and training the child needs for subsequent learning. Therefore, the home support a child receives from the parents and siblings is a key factor in the child's learning experience outcome.

In the context of the above assertion, Nwachukwu, Onwukwe, Evans-Kemka, Azorji, Nguma, (2024) indicated that the home environment means the family background of the learners, and includes all the human and material resources present at home that influence the learners' education and living, as well

as the socializing facilities available in the house. Socializing facilities, Nwachukwu et al, further pointed out include social interaction, open communication, friendliness and family fun time through games among family members. They noted that the home environment provides the child his or her first exposure to social relationship, creates the impression that may ultimately last a life time and sharpens the child's potentials for subsequent attainment in formal learning. These assertions agree with Malik, (2002) and Umudi, (2025) that the home is the source of early stimulation and informal learning and experiences in life. Therefore, the home environment is a strong support base for children's social and cognitive development.

Within the home environment, the family constitutes a social unit, where the child often interacts and socialises with the parents, siblings, and these acts are contributory factors which facilitate acquisition of knowledge, values and skills both informally and formally. Accordingly, Hussaini (2024) described the family as the first socializing agent for the child which also functions to prepare the child for school and to influence his or her attitude towards school.

The assertion posits the home as the foundation where the child's intellectual development is laid and the family as a foundational social institution from which all other institutions develop. It portrays the family as an important agency of education which also exercises an immediate and even an everlasting influence on the behaviour, character, conduct and personality of its members. Thus, the home is the child's first educator and remains where the learner's early experiential background is set. According to Saminu (2021), any attempt by the school to educate the child without proper regard to the conditions of his home environment is bound to lead to confusion, and ultimately low academic performance.

Academic performance, according to Hussaini (2024), is considered as a complex students' behaviour that inspires a number of abilities, like sharp memory, previous knowledge, or aptitude, and psychological factors (social relationship and interactions among family members).

These abilities point to learning, which Hussaini asserted is the knowledge or skill acquired through study, and are further reflected in the way the pupils respond to environmental, social, emotional and physical incentives as well as the understanding of new information, according to Gross (2010). Further, Gross in 'Psychology: The Science of Mind and Behaviour', described academic performance as 'the assessment of a student's ability in a variety of academic areas: classroom performance, graduation rates and standardized test results, which are commonly used by teachers to evaluate a student's accomplishment'.

Researches have been conducted on many 'factors that contribute to academic performance'. The majority of these researches concentrated on three intervening elements; 'parents' (family causal factor), 'teachers' (academic causal factor), and 'students' (personal causal factor), Daiz, (2003) and Olushola, Taofeek, and Olumide (2015) and Onyekwere et al (2018).

However, in spite of the provisions of the necessary support tools by parents, schools and other institutions, students' academic performance has continued to be worrisome, especially at the foundational stage of education. For instance, in recent time, students' performance in the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) – a terminal examination for junior secondary schools -- has dropped considerably, according to WAEC, (2023).

Also, students' mass failure of English Language and mathematics in the West African Examination Council (WAEC, June 2024 report), and even the most recent Post UMTE Analysis of the 2025 Joint

Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) – university entrance examinations – generated general public outcry in Nigeria. The Guardian newspaper (May 27, 2025) also pointed out that the issue of poor academic performance has been a major concern to governments, schools and parents. The paper's report corroborated Frempong, Asare-Bediako, and Aboagye, (2016) assertions as well. Also, Orlu (2013) research on *Environmental Influence on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students* had suggested the need for a holistic approach to effectively support the academic performance of students.

It is against this background that the current research sought to investigate the Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Achievement in English Language in Kuje Area Council, in the Federal Capital Territory, (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Malik, (2002) asserted that the home is often the first and most insistent environment that has influence on the educational development of the child, hence the first place a youngster learns about the world outside of school. A key component of home environment is the family that provides the child the pool from which he or she draws the resources needed to build his or her initial group of friends, Owens-Sogolo and Osunde (2024). The family therefore has been described, as the child's 'first educator and remains where the learner's early experiential background is set', (Saminu, (2021).

The aforementioned assertions confirmed earlier studies by Nwachukwu and Agulaana (2002), Epstein (2011), Grant and Ray (2013) that the family is the primary and most important human institution for the socialization of the child. These studies noted that a child's social experiences within the family influences his or her behaviour within and outside the immediate environment.

The above assertions are corroborated by Hussaini's (2024) perspective on Social and Emotional Development in ECCE which indicated that the family provides the social nutrients the child needs for normal physical, cognitive, psychomotor and social development. It concluded that a child develops and builds his or her self- image and projects his or her self-actualization from the home based on the vibrant social relationships among family members and transfers same to the external environment. Similarly, Castro, Exposito-Casas, Lopez-Martin, Lizasoain, Asencio, and Goviria (2015) indicated that parental involvement is an individual right of responsibility for families and a social need, and that without the positive cooperation of parents and schools, it would be impossible to reach the high standard set for educational outcomes by the demanding society. Parentkind, (2024) stated that parents' involvement in the education of their children influences them to perform better on a wide range of measures. This implies that parents' participation in the learning activities of their children would encourage them and help to improve the learning outcomes of their children.

According to Ogbemudia and Aiasa (2013) the home equally constitutes the child's reference point for evaluating the behaviour expectations and performances against those of children from other families. The atmosphere at home and how the family encourages them towards education, contribute to children's performance in school, according to Otu, (2017).

Thus, the home environment and atmosphere are dominant make-up of the child's personality since the home environment is the child's first contact with the society and its social environment. The home environment equally constitutes the child's reference point for evaluating his or her behaviour expectations and performances against children from other families as explained by Ogbemudia and Aiasa, (2013).

The condition of the home is a significant factor in a child's learning outcome, according to Ndifon, (2017) who posited that where the home atmosphere is devoid of social interaction, and communication is stiff and regimented; lacking the necessary ambience for deeper talk, much less discussion on school activities- homework, specific subjects, a learner would hardly receive the push to excel. The research further asserted that the lack of social engagements, which generate, nurture and sustain cordial relationship at home, tended to negate aspects of the child's growth process, and the drive to excel academically. Therefore, the absence of positive atmosphere at home may rub off negatively on the child's psycho-social competences and may ultimately hinder the child's emotional development, stability and drive for success in education.

According to Otu (2017), a child thrives where the home atmosphere is friendly enabling regular interactions with family members who are accessible by the child to: ask questions which elicit responses, freely disclose obstacles he or she may be grappling with at school on any subject of study, and receive encouraging support. Such a child will be open to fresh ideas, likely to put in more efforts to understand lessons and aspires to achieve academic excellence. The conditions for learning at home must be favourable and adequate to produce the desired result. Therefore, home environment is not an abstract concept. Instead, as indicated by Nwachukwu et al, (2024), it is the combination of the physical and the psychological environments. Both have positive impact on the physical, mental and emotional wellbeing of the child, according to Onwukwe, Anyanwu and Agommuoh (2017), Owens- Sogolo and Osunde (2024). Besides, a study conducted by Clark and Goyder (2007) indicated that the teaching learning process carried out at school is incomplete without the support of the home.

Series of researches such as Al- Shamari, Saguban, Pasay-an, Altheban, and Al-Shamari (2017), Olatunji, Aghimien, Oke, and Olushola (2016), Dzever (2015), Byoung –Suk and Christopher, (2015) conducted on likely factors which could affect academic achievements of pupils indicated that parents' socio-economic status, parents' family income, parents level of education, parents' occupational status, parents' involvement in their children's school activities, parenting styles', and school-based factors, were some of the variables. Notably, the studies noted a correlation between the social variables and academic achievements of learners.

Besides, Patton (2019) in another study revealed that the instructional techniques used in schools which relied solely on teachers have not yielded the desired results because learners tend to achieve more when their parents are involved in the education process. However, it is not known whether home environment has any correlation with pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, (FCT), Abuja.

Thus, the Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, (FCT), Abuja, is not known. The current study therefore sought whether there is any influence of home environment on pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, (FCT), Abuja.

Statement of Problem

Both the West African Examination Council (WEAC) and the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), have repeatedly expressed concern over students' worrisome failure rate in English language, Salahu, (2020). This was particularly obvious in the 2024 WAEC and the JAMB examination March 2025 results. This study seeks to investigate the Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council in the FCT, Abuja.

Purpose of Study

The study investigates the Influence of Home Environment on Pupils' Achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, FCT, Abuja. The study is expected to achieve the following objectives;

1. Find out the relationship between home environment and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council.
2. Investigate the relationship between interaction among family members and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the conduct of the study:

1. What is the relationship between home environment and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council?
2. What is the relationship between the interaction among family members and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested namely:

HO₁: There is no significant Relationship Between Home Environment and Pupils' Achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council.

HO₂: There is no significant Relationship Between Interaction Among Family Members and Pupils' Achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted the correlational method. It is a method that is used to show whether a relationship exists between two or more variables, essentially whether independent variables have some influence on a dependent variable, Akande (2019).

In this study, the correlational method was considered appropriate because it was used to investigate whether a relationship exists between home environment and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council, and whether a relationship exists between interaction among family members and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all the 880 public primary school pupils consisting of the 559 institutions managed by Local Education Authorities and the 321 Early Child Care Development Education Centres in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The target population consisted of 4,336

primary five pupils in public schools.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The researcher used Yamane's Formula at a 5% margin of error on the population size of 4,336. The sample size of 360 pupils was chosen for the study using simple random sampling to select them from four out of the 105 public primary schools in Kuje Area Council. Multi-stage sampling technique involving district, urban and semi-urban settlements was used to select Kuje Area Council out of the six area councils.

Instrumentation

The instruments tagged "Home Environment Support Questionnaire" (HESQ) consisting of nine (9) items on the relationship between home environment and pupils' academic achievement in English language in Kuje Area Council and "Pupils' Interaction and Achievement Questionnaire" (PIAQ) consisting of seven (7) items were developed by the researcher and directly administered on the pupils within the age bracket of 10–11 years by hand through the help of respective class teachers.

The instrument consisted of 400 questionnaires (100 per school) and were distributed within four days. Only 380 were returned within the two-week time frame allotted for the exercise, while 20 were not returned at all. Of the 380 questionnaires returned, 10 were mutilated while another 10 had unfilled spaces and they could not be accepted as properly filled.

Validity of the Instrument

Three experts from the University of Abuja and the FCT College of Education, Zuba in Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation were engaged to ascertain the validation of the instrument and to ensure that it meets both face and content validity.

Reliability of the Instrument

To test the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered them on ten pupils that were not involved in the study. A test–retest method was adopted within a three-week interval and the result obtained showed a reliability coefficient of 0.64.

Statistical Analysis

The researcher analysed the data collected to answer the research questions by using frequency and mean, respectively. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). The modified Likert scale structure (Strongly Agree = 4, Agree = 3, Strongly Disagree = 2, Disagree = 1) was used to measure the data obtained and a benchmark of 2.50 was set.

Results

Table 1: Relationship between home environment and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council?

S/NO	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remarks
1	I often discuss with my father in English Language which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	168	126	44	22	3.22	Agree
2	I often discuss with my mother in English Language which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	156	136	44	32	3.2	Agree
3	I often discuss with my older siblings in English Language which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	110	160	70	40	3.06	Agree
4	My father corrects my reading of English passages which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	162	108	56	34	3.11	Agree
5	My mother corrects my reading of English passages which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	180	130	40	10	3.33	Agree
6	My older siblings correct my reading of English passages which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	120	150	70	20	3.03	Agree
7	My father assists me to do my English language assignments which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	116	114	106	24	2.89	Agree
8	My mother assists me to do my English language assignments which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	144	136	72	8	3.15	Agree
9	My older siblings assist me to do my English assignments which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	112	108	90	50	2.78	Agree

N= 360; Source: Field Study, 2024.

The analysis of table 1 established the tremendous influence of home environment had on pupils' achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje. Results from items 1 to 9 were above the 2.5 bench mark for acceptance of the research outcome. Items 5 and 1 on mothers' correction of pupils' reading of English passages and discussion with fathers in English language recorded the highest mean scores of 3.33 and 3.22, respectively. Although item 9 that sought response on siblings' assistance with take home assignment recorded the lowest mean score of 2.78, it scaled over the 2.5 bench mark for acceptance of the result.

The result confirmed the influence of a supportive 'home environment on academic performance of pupils' and agrees with earlier studies conducted by Dzever (2015) and Byoung –Suk and Christopher (2015) which indicated that 'parents' involvement in their children's academic activities and parenting styles' do have positive influence on the children's academic performance in school.

Table 2: Relationship between family members' interaction and pupils' achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area councils?

S/NO	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remarks
10	My discussion with my family members in English language is related to my English Language achievement in school.	160	120	68	12	3.19	positive
11	My friendly discussion with my family members in English language is related to my English Language achievement in school.	120	170	60	10	3.11	positive
12	My purposeful discussion with my family members in English language is related to my English Language achievement in school.	148	140	56	16	3.17	positive
13	My discussion with my family members in good English is related to my English Language achievement in school.	190	130	50	0	3.47	positive
14	My discussion with my family members in English language motives me to do well English Language in school.	170	128	42	20	3.24	positive
15	I often play games in English language with my family members English language which is related to my English Language achievement in school.	114	140	80	26	2.95	positive
16	Generally, the home support I get is related to my achievement in English language in school.	180	114	42	24	3.25	positive

Table 2 shows that all the items were positive. The analysis of the items showed a relationship between family members’ interaction and pupils’ achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area council. Item 13 on pupils’ discussion with family members in good English ranked highest with 3.47 mean score, general home support recorded 3.25 mean score, while item 15 on playing games generated a mean score of 2.95, thus indicating that interaction with family members was related to pupils’ achievement in English language in schools.

It agrees with Ndifon’s, (2017) assertion that children are more comfortable in homes where there is warmth, confidence, attention and helping behaviour. Helping behaviour refers to social habits; communication, interaction, friendliness, and parents’ deliberate inculcation in their children the tendency to develop and sustain study and other healthy attitudinal habits, which would subsequently enhance academic achievement and goals in life.

Analysis of Hypothesis

HO₁. There is no significant relationship between home environment and pupils’ achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the FCT.

Table 3: Relationship between home environment and pupils’ achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the FCT.

		Home environment	Pupils’ Academic Achievement
Home environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.212**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Pupils’ Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	.212**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

****.** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The Table 3 indicates that the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient $r = .212$ with N of 360 is statistically significant at 0.05 level and the $p = 0.000$. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant relationship between home environment and pupils’ achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the FCT” is therefore rejected.

This means that there is significant relationship between home environment and pupils’ achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the FCT.

HO₂. There is no significant relationship between interaction among family members and pupils’ academic achievement in English Language in Kuje Area Council.

Table 4: Relationship between interaction among family members and pupils’ academic achievement in English Language in Kuje Area Council

		Family Members interaction	Pupils’ Academic Achievement
Family Members interaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.371**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Pupils’ Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	.371**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

**** . Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 4 shows Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed). The result suggests that the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient $r = .371$ with N of 360 is statistically significant at 0.05 level ($p = 0.000$).

Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that “There is no significant relationship between interaction among family members and students’ academic achievement in English Language in Kuje Area Council” is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is significant relationship between interaction among family members and pupils’ achievement in English language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council of the FCT.

Discussion

The study showed that interaction among family members in good English has impact on children’s academic achievement in English Language in public primary schools in Kuje Area Council. Similarly, deep maternal interest in their wards’ study impacted on their performances as evident by mothers’ correction of their children’s reading of English passages, which recorded the highest mean score of 3.33, and thus contributed immensely to their achievement in English language in schools. The findings are supported by Aweh’s (2017) extrinsic motivational theory that states that individuals are spurred to achieve by external forces; either by reward or deliberate persuasion to specific purpose. The findings equally affirmed Falemu and Akinwunmi (2017) and Ndifon’s (2017) assertion that children perform well in school when parents assist and encourage them to prepare their homework and provide a comfortable social ambience that encourages learning.

Thus, home environment and interaction among family members tend to stimulate the child’s interest

and commitment to accomplish academic excellence and other goals set before him or her.

Recommendations

After analyzing the data collected and drawing conclusions from the findings, the researcher recommends that:

1. Parents should deliberately participate as much as possible in their children's learning of the English language by going through and constantly checking their notes, class works, and assist where possible, in their take home assignments.
2. Parents should endeavour to get involved in recreational activities and games which are fertile grounds for general interactions and discussions on their wards' study of English language in school.

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